

Administrative communication and its relationship to job performance among workers in the sports administration.

A field study for the Directorate of Youth and Sports for the Wilayat of M'sila.

ZAOUI AZZEDINE¹ ; LOUNAS ABDELLAH² ; MANSOURI NABIL³

^{1,2,3} Institute of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities, University of Mohand Akli Oulhadj Bouira , Modern science laboratory in physical and sports activities smaps

¹ az.zaoui@univ-bouira.dz, ² lounas@univ-bouira.dz, ³ n.mansouri@univ-bouira.dz

ARTICLE INFORMATION

Original Research Paper

Received: 12/01/2021

Accepted: 12/04/2021

Published: 01/06/2021

Keywords: Administrative Communication – Job performance – Sports administration.

Abstract

The study aims to identify the relationship between administrative communication and job performance among employees in the sports administration of the Directorate of Youth and Sports in the Wilayat of M'sila. For this purpose, we used the descriptive survey approach on a sample of 34 surveyed individuals. To collect data, we used a questionnaire tool. After collecting the results and treating them statistically, a correlation was found between administrative communication and the job performance of the study sample, and on this basis the study recommended giving employees full freedom in their communication with the administration in order to raise their concerns and for performance at the level.

Corresponding author: ZAOUI AZZEDINE,
e-mail: az.zaoui@univ-bouira.dz

I. Introduction :

The great development in the means of communication at the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century brought many unprecedented advantages. In fact, the ease of the flow of communication and knowledge materials in the world has contributed to the narrowing borders and barriers, so that the world became like a small village with interconnected parts. Developing countries, including Algeria, have attempted to acquire communication technology and to create national communication industries to confirm their cultural and industrial presence at the local and international levels. Besides, the steady growth and continuous diversity of new media has led to more accurate communication of all kinds, which has increased the effectiveness of communication messages, and time, effort and money reduction and has provided the opportunity to benefit from the advantages of communications in general, and communications in organizations in particular or what is known as administrative communication within organizations. (Fodil Dillo, 1995.)

The importance of administrative communication in the organization increases because of the vital role played by organizations in their economic or service formula in achieving prosperity and providing the increasing and developing needs of society, which requires raising the level of functional performance of the actors in these organizations to face all the challenges of this new era, which requires speed, accuracy and good planning in communicating and understanding orders and instructions from the higher administration to the employees to run and control the work of the organization, in addition to the knowledge of all the problems, their developments and obstacles that limit the ability of employees in their performance. Zahaf Mohamed (2016) .

MacDavid and Harary state that the concept of a group is defined by an organized pattern of two or more individuals linked to each other for a specific goal, and that this pattern provides its members with a set of role relationships and a set of standards that regulate the group's function, and the function of each of its members. Fiedler adds that the concept of a group is that it is a cooperative group of individuals facing a common fate and

depending on each other, so that if an accident affects one of them, it provokes it and reflects on the rest of its members. Hamzawy Hakim (2012) Through the importance of communication as a science and a process that entered all fields of life in societies, and that the institution is part of society, institutions have become dependent on communication in achieving their goals. In fact, the development of institutions has led to the development of communication methods to meet their needs and achieve their goals. Many researchers have undertaken a precedent study of the issue of administrative communication and its relationship with job performance, such as Bouaitit Djalal Eddine study (2009) under the title “The Relationship of Organizational Communication with Job Performance”, which has concluded that there is a positive intermediate correlation between downward communication and job performance in addition to upward communication and job performance among executive employees, in addition to the study by Mohamed Seifeddine in (2009), under the title ‘The Impact of Organizational Communication on the Level of Job Performance’, which has concluded that the work environment in the study sample is at some extent suitable for practicing organizational communication, in addition to that organizational communication plays an important role in improving the job performance of individuals, also the study of Mohamed Zahaf (2016), under the title of ‘Official Communication and its Relationship to Organizational Loyalty”, a field study of the Youth and Sports Directorate of the Province of M’sila. The general objective of the study is to identify the nature of the relationship between formal communication and organizational loyalty. The main findings of the study: the existence of a weak correlation between formal communication and organizational loyalty among the directorate’s employees. As for the relationship between upward communication and organizational loyalty among the study sample, it have found a weak inverse relationship, there inexistence of statistical differences between the answers of the employees in the variables (gender, age, experience, educational level) in addition to the study of Mohamed Seddik LOU and Kamel BENMESBAH (2019) entitled: “The impact of the administrative communication strategy on the

level of Job Performance of Employees in the Junior Sector of the Algerian Professional Football Clubs'. The study aims to identify the reality of the communication strategy within Algerian football clubs in the youth sector. The most important results reached are the importance that must be given to the downward and upward communication because it reflects the reality of the communication process in the Algerian professional football clubs in the youth sector, in addition to the Gallup Institute study (1998): He has studied the role of the mission and organizational culture in the success of the work. The survey conducted by the Globe Institute in the United States on more than one hundred thousand users in hundreds of different units through 24 big companies, who are over 25 years old, has found some important data by the use of the questionnaire as a tool in collecting Data. In spite of the essay speech published about the task of communication, the survey has concluded that the most important thing in communication is the relationships between managers and their working groups. (Bob Garratt: The Twelve Organizational Capabilities. Translation in Arabic: Hisham Dajani (2004, p. 106))

Also the study of Fateh Yagoubi, Abdelmalek Kermich and Hamlaoui Ameer (2020) entitled "Effective Communication and its Role in Achieving Positive Results among some Algerian Sports Clubs". This study aims to identify the role of the communication process within Algerian clubs in achieving positive results at the sports performance level. The most fundamental findings of the study are to give great importance to communication and its means within Algerian clubs, as it allows the transfer of experiences, skills and ideas between heads of sports clubs and their coaches, in addition to the study of Mohamed Guettaf, Bouras Mohamed, Bait Aissa jouan (2020), requirements for the quality of academic communication, and this study aims to highlight the most important requirements necessary to achieve the quality of communication and academic communication within the university. The most important results of the study are to ensure communication and constructive interaction between the teacher and the active learner in order to reach an effective communication process that achieves the quality of communication within

the university and to reach the intended requirements. Dahmani Naima, Djouadi Khaled (2017) “The degree and importance of administrative competencies in achieving job satisfaction among the employees of the sports administration for the Province of Mila”. The study aims to identify the importance of administrative competencies in achieving job satisfaction, and has concluded that there is the importance of administrative competencies in achieving the job satisfaction level for the employees of the Sports Administration and a high degree of administrative competence.

Good high performance, which is the result of an effort, whether muscular or intellectual, made by an individual or group to reach a specific achievement to reach or to achieve predetermined objectives, based on the exploitation of available resources and the inputs of the institution at the lowest cost and a high productivity with preserving the health and comfort of the employee, which gives the institution its position and guarantees its survival, continuity and distinction within successful companies. Thus, our study attempts to focus on the relationship between administrative communication and job performance in sports in which study the reality of administrative communications and its relationship with the performance of employees. (Rabhi Mustafa, Adnan Mahmoud, 2005, p. 35)

Hence, the problem of the study lies in the following main question: Is there a correlation between administrative communication and job performance among employees in the sports administration of the Directorate of Youth and Sports in the Province of M'sila?

II. Method and tools:

1- Sample Selection Methods.

- The sample: Our study sample consisted of (34) members of the sports administration in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in the Province of M'sila, was chosen by the method of comprehensive survey, due to the small population of the study consisting of (41) individuals from whom we excluded (07) who was subject to an exploratory study in our study, so the sample is the study population.

2- Study Procedures: They include:

2-1 - Approach: We used in our study descriptive survey approach with correlation relationship due to its relevance to the nature of the topic and the objectives of the study.

2-2 - Defining the variables and the method of its measurement.

The independent variable: is the administrative communication

The dependent variable: is job performance.

2-3- The tool: our study relies on the questionnaire as a tool for collecting information and data. The questionnaire was divided into four axes:

The First Topic: 8 phrases on the communication lost to the employees of the sports administration.

The Second Topic: 8 phrases on the upward communication of the employees of the sports administration.

The Third Topic: 8 phrases on the upward communication of the employees of the sports administration.

The Fourth Topic: 22 phrases on the job performance of the employees of the sports administration.

The answers to the phrases of the questionnaire are graded between always, never, sometimes.

2-4 The Psychometric Properties of the Tool:

The Validity Of The Experts:

We presented it to a group of professors of different academic degrees who had experience in the field of scientific research, who were five (05) in order to be judged. All the professors have agreed on the suitability of the form after introducing the necessary and useful amendments, and they have agreed on the validity of the content of the form and the achievement of its purpose and on the extent of its sincerity and efficiency in measuring the study variables. By means of the observations made within the framework of apparent honesty, the necessary modifications have been made, as for the first topic related to organizational communication,

Adding two phrases to equalize the dimensions of the communication.

Stability: Before presenting the questionnaire to the research sample, the applicability of the latter must be checked. That is why we have used the test-retest method by calculating the Test-Retest coefficient, which reflects

the degree to of the relationship between the scores obtained when it was first applied and the scores obtained at the re-application. That is why we have chosen a sample consisting of 7 employees, who were randomly drawn from the nominal list and later removed from the final sample. After a period of 15 days, the questionnaire was redistributed as these individuals were excluded from the original study sample, then we have calculated The correlation coefficient and the results were as follows:

The sample equals 07 individuals

Table (01): Correlation coefficient

Sample	correlation coefficient
07 individuals	0.62

2-5 - Statistical Tools

Spss:

Correlation scale, t-student and anova differences test

III. Results:

Table No. 2: shows the results of the (t-test) on the degree of the existence of differences in the answers of the research individuals with regard to gender and job performance.

Topic	gender	n	Mean	calculated T	significance	degree of freedom	significance value	Decision
Job perfor	Male	25	2,4818	0.215	0.169	32	0.05	Not significant
	Female	09	2,4596					

- Analysis of Table No. 2: shows that there are no statistically significant differences between the answers of males and females on the topic of job performance. We notice in the table that the calculated t value is greater than the significance value, so there are no statistically significant differences due to the gender variable at the level of significance. (0.05).

- *Table No. 03: shows the arithmetic means, standard deviations, and the correlation coefficient of the four topics with the job performance of employees at the Youth and Sports Directorate of the Province of M'sila.*

Topics	arithmetic average	standard deviations	correlation coefficient	type of relationship
downward communication topic	2.54	0.58	- 0.26	Inverse relationship
Upward communication topic	2.45	0.65	0.18	positive relationship
Horizontal communication topic	2.29	0.61	0.17	positive relationship
Administrative communication	2.38	0.61	0.19	positive relationship
Job performance	2.36	0.58		

- Analysis of Table No. 03: Table No. 03 shows that: With regard to the downward communication topic, the arithmetic mean is of (2.54), the standard deviation is (0.58), and the correlation coefficient is (-0.26), which is an inverse correlation, that is, there is an inverse correlation between the downward management Administrative communication and Job performance at the Directorate of Youth and Sports in the Province of M'sila, which are significant values at the level (0.05).

- For the upward communication topic, the arithmetic mean is (2.45), the standard deviation is (0.65), and the correlation coefficient is (0.18), which is a direct correlation relationship, that is, there is a positive correlation between the upward administrative communication and job performance at the Youth and Sports Directorate of the Province of M'sila, which are significant values at the level of (0.05).

- As to the horizontal communication topic, the arithmetic mean is (2.29), the standard deviation is (0.61), and the correlation coefficient is (0.17), which is a direct correlation relationship, that is, the existence of a direct correlation between the horizontal administrative communication and job performance at the Youth and Sports Directorate of the Province of M'sila, which are significant values at the level of (0.05).

IV. Discussing the Results :

Regarding test of sex, age, educational level, and seniority factors, through which the researcher aimed to ensure that there are no differences between the employees of the Youth and Sports Directorate in the Province of M'sila due to the abovementioned demographic factors. The researcher has concluded that there are no relevant statistically significance differences attributed to demographic and personal factors (gender, age, educational level, seniority) and this indicates that there is no effect of the job performance of the employees of the Youth and Sports Directorate on these variables. Therefore, we can say that the hypothesis has been fulfilled and our study is consistent with by the study of Mohamed Zahaf (2016) which also has concluded that there is no statistically significant difference due to demographic and personal factors (gender, age, educational level, seniority) as well by the study of Chouaib Mazouz and Omrani Ahmed Hakim (June 2020) in the absence of the differences.

Through the answers of the study sample individuals about the topic of downward communication and job performance, we found that there is an inverse correlation and that the administration mostly in communicating with them aims to present decisions for execution only, that is, it does not consult them about their work matters, and this what was confirmed by the study of "Mohamed Zahaf" (2016) about the existence of a weak inverse relationship between official communication and organizational loyalty, in addition to the study of Mohamed Seddik Lout and Kamel Ben Mesbah (2019), which has concluded to give importance to downward communication because it reflects the reality of the communication process in Algerian professional football clubs at the youth sector. Even if the relationship is inverse, the correlation exists, which fulfills the hypothesis that there is a relationship between the downward communication and the job performance of the employees of the Youth and Sports Directorate of the Province of M'sila.

Through the answers of the study sample individuals on the topic of upward communication and job performance, we found that there is direct correlation, and this indicates that the greater the upward communication,

the greater the job performance of the employees of the Youth and Sports Directorate of the Province of M'sila, or the less the upward communication, the lower the performance: This hypothesis states that the upward communication in which employees contact the directorate through the immediate supervisor and the theoretical background show that in the upward communication the employee gives to his manager data about his work, and the problems encountered at work that require the intervention of higher authorities to solve them. The writers Chester Barnard and Mary Parker Follett have stressed the importance of emerging communications. They have emphasized that leadership consists in accepting instructions they receive voluntarily and with more conviction because of the authority of the chiefs to issue the decisions necessary to the executive levels. This is confirmed by the study of Mohamed Zahaf (2016) on the existence of a weak correlation between upward official communication and organizational loyalty, and also the study of Fateh Yagoubi, Abdelmalek Kermich and Hamalaoui Ameer (2020) to give great importance to communication and its means within Algerian clubs as it permits the transfer of expertise, skills and ideas between the presidents of sports clubs and their coaches. Despite the low level of the correlation of upward communication and job performance at the Directorate of Youth and Sports in the Province of M'sila, the relationship exists, that is there is a correlation between the upward administrative communication and job performance at the Youth and Sports Directorate of the Province of M'sila. In fact, the hypothesis has been fulfilled.

It concerns horizontal administrative communication and its relationship to job performance. The results of the study have showed the existence of a positive correlation for the correlation coefficients between horizontal administrative communication and job performance, that is to say, the more horizontal administrative communication increases, the higher the job performance or vice versa, the more the horizontal administrative communication decreases the lower job performance. Statistical analysis, and the researcher's indications on that the horizontal communication show that the value and effectiveness of the horizontal communication type

enables individuals to discuss work problems with colleagues and try to listen to their views on the job performance process, comparing their performance with the performance of their colleagues, raising the morale and organizational behavior within the organization. In fact, the relationship between colleagues is an important tool in this type because of its role in improving performance, and this was the results of the study of Fateh Yaqoubi, Abdelmalek Kermich and Hamlaoui Ameer (2020) in the study of effective communication and its role in achieving positive results in some Algerian sports clubs. The researchers believe that the absence of distribution of tasks, of specification of responsibilities and the lack of respect for the organizational chart are all factors that disable administrative communication process and prevent the achievement of the desired goals and that the effectiveness of administrative communication consists of working as one group and a new method of communication, placing suitable individuals and competencies in the right place and at the right time to achieve the goals. Also, the study of Guettaf Mohamed, Bouras Mohamed, Bait Aissa Jouane (2020), has emphasized the guarantee of constructive communication and interaction between the teacher and the effective learner in order to reach an effective communication process achieving the quality of communication. In fact, this shows that horizontal communication at the Directorate of Youth and Sports suffers from some difficulties that have led to the weakness of this relationship, but it does exist, that is, the existence of a correlation. Thus, we can say that there is a correlation between horizontal communication and job performance at the Youth and Sports for the Province of M'sila, which means that the hypothesis was fulfilled.

V. Conclusion:

The results obtained in this study which concerns one of important topics of administration and organization, which is the administrative communication process and its relationship with job performance for employees at the sports administration filed, have revealed the necessity to present a set of the following suggestions: Giving complete freedom to the employees of the institution not only in their communication with the administration and

communicating their concerns, but with the need to involve them in the decision-making process within the institution within the framework of laws that regulate these freedoms; increasing and developing the capabilities of employees by intensifying and promoting the training processes in the field of communication and understanding the collected information that have a direct or indirect impact on their performance; conducting a study to find out the attitudes of both the higher and lower levels of administrators and users towards all other administrative processes of planning, organizing, controlling, directing and their role in the type of effective communication that helps in the good performance of all the actors in the company; conducting similar studies of administrative communication by introducing variables conducted in the study such as: administrative communication and its relationship to administrative creativity from the viewpoint of employees of the Directorate of Youth and Sports, in addition to the administrative communication and its role in activating the performance process within the administrative structure, in addition to the role of administrative communication in reducing the psychological pressure of employees, and administrative communication and its role in evaluating the employee's job performance.

VI. References:

- 1 - Bob Garratt (2004): The Twelve Organizational Capabilities. Translation in Arabic: Hisham Dajani, p. 106.
- 2 - Mohamed Zahaf (2016): "Official Communication and its Relationship to Organizational Loyalty", The Scientific Journal of the Sciences and Techniques of Physical and Sports Activities, Mostaganem University, Algeria, Nà. 13
- 3- Mohamed Seddik Lout and Kamel Ben Mesbah (2019): "Impact of the strategy of administrative communication on the level of Functional performance of workers in the junior sector in the Algerian professional football teams", Scientific Journal of the Sciences and Techniques of Physical and Sports Activities, Mostaganem University of Algeria, No. 1, Volume 16, pp. 98-79
- 4 - Fateh Yagoubi, Abdelmalek Kermich and Hamlaoui Ameer (2020) "effective communication and its role in achieving reproductive results among some Algerian sports clubs", the Scientific Journal of the Sciences and Techniques of Physical and

Sports Activities, Mostaganem University of Algeria, Volume 17 / No.: 2 (duplicate) December -, pp: 238- 250

5 - Guettaf Mohamed, Bouras Mohamed, Bait Aissa Jouane (2020), “requirements for the quality of academic communication from the students' point of view”, The Scientific Journal of the Sciences and Techniques of Physical Activities and Sports - Mostaganem - Volume 17, the first issue repeated.

6- Dahmani Naima, Jaouadi Khaled December (2017) “The Degree and Importance of Administrative Competencies in Achieving Job Satisfaction Among the Staff of the Sports Administration of the Province of Mila”, Scientific Journal of Science and Technology for Physical Activities and Sports - Mostaganem – No. 14.

7- Chaib Maazouz and Omrani Ahmed Hakim, (June 2020.) “The contribution of the Application of Human Resource Management Strategies in Sports Institutions to the Success of Sports Professionalism in Algeria”, The Scientific Journal of the Sciences and Techniques of Physical Activities and Sports, Mostaganem Algeria, Volume 17, No. 1 (bis)

8- Boufetta of Mohamed Saifeddin in (2009), under the title “The Impact of Organizational Communications on the Level of Job Performance”

9- Garry Dessler (1992): Fundamentals of Management, "Modern Principles and Practices", Translation in Arabic: Abdelkader Mohamed Abdelkader, Al-Marrikh Publishing House, Riyadh

10- Rabhi Mustafa Aliane, Adnan Mahmoud al-Toubasi: “Communication and Public Relations”, Safaa Publishing House 200 and Distribution, Amman, 1st Edition.

11- Fadil Deliou (2007) “History of Communication Methods” - House of Thought Poles - Constantine, Algeria.

12- Allen, N, Meyer, J (1990): The Measurement and Antecedents of Affective, Continuance and Normative Commitment to the Organization, Journal of occupational Psychology

13- Hamzawy Hakim (2012), The Scientific Journal of the Sciences and Techniques of Physical and Physiological Activities, 10th Issue., Mostaganem Algeria, December 31, 2013